

The Dual role of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) in Cancer: Driver of Tumorigenesis and Therapeutic Target

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Abstract

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) exhibit a dual role in cancer development and therapy. At physiological concentrations, ROS function as essential signaling molecules that regulate cell growth, differentiation, and immune responses. Elevated ROS levels disrupt redox homeostasis, induce oxidative stress, and cause DNA damage and genomic instability. Increased ROS activate oncogenic signaling pathways, including PI3K/AKT, MAPK, and NF- κ B, thereby promoting cancer initiation, progression, angiogenesis, and metastasis. Cancer cells tolerate elevated ROS due to altered metabolism but adapt by upregulating antioxidant systems. Therapeutic strategies leverage this vulnerability: ROS-generating agents can exceed the oxidative threshold of cancer cells, leading to selective cytotoxicity, while antioxidants may protect normal tissues from therapy-induced oxidative damage. Emerging approaches involve ROS-modulating drugs, nanotechnology-based delivery systems, and combination regimens with conventional therapies. However, tumor heterogeneity, adaptive antioxidant responses, and the absence of robust biomarkers continue to impede clinical translation. This review provides an overview of ROS biology in cancer, current therapeutic interventions, and prospective strategies for targeting redox balance.

Keywords: ROS, oxidative stress, redox signaling, cancer metabolism, tumor microenvironment, targeted therapy.

1. Introduction

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) refer to a collection of highly reactive substances that incorporate oxygen, including free radicals such as superoxide ($O_2^{\cdot -}$) and the hydroxyl radical (OH^{\cdot}), as well as nonradicals such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Although ROS are usually discussed in the context of oxidative stress and cell damage, they can also serve as important signaling molecules that control a range of cellular activities, such as cell proliferation, differentiation, immune response, and apoptosis [1], [2]. ROS are mainly generated as byproducts of mitochondrial respiration that occurs within the inner mitochondrial membrane during aerobic metabolisms [3]. Nevertheless, other cellular mechanisms of ROS generation include cytochrome P450 enzyme activity, peroxisomal fatty acid oxidation, and inflammatory reactions [4], [5]. In physiological circumstances, the ROS play a role in cell signaling and defense. ROS are important for cellular redox homeostasis and act as secondary messengers in various signaling pathways at low to moderate levels [6], [7]. For example, ROS can mediate the immune response by activating NF-

kB and other redox-sensitive transcription factors that control the expression of inflammatory and immune-activating genes [8], [9]. Moreover, ROS also participates in the activation of kinases (MAPK and PI3K/AKT) that regulate cellular survival, growth, and proliferation [10]. However, once ROS levels become too high, they overwhelm the body's antioxidant defense mechanisms, causing oxidative stress [11]. Oxidative stress is a state in which the generation of ROS exceeds the cell's capacity to counteract it with endogenous antioxidants, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione, and catalase [12], [13], [14]. The result of this imbalance is cellular damage, such as lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and DNA damage, which might impair normal cellular functioning and lead to diseases, including cancer [15], [16]. Cancer is defined as an illness in which cells fail to proliferate, exhibit genomic instability, and evade cell death. ROS have been involved in cancer development and progression [17]. On the one hand, an increase in the level of ROS leads to tumorigenesis through the increase of genetic mutations, angiogenesis, and cell survival [18], [19], [20]. ROS activate various oncogenic pathways, such as PI3K/AKT, MAPK, and NF-kB, which control key processes, such as proliferation, invasion, and immune evasion [21]. Genomic instability caused by ROS also promotes mutagenesis, leading to genetic changes that drive the conversion of normal cells into cancer cells [22]. Indicatively, ROS inactivates p53, a tumor suppressor of critical importance since it causes genomic instability and apoptosis resistance in most cancers [20]. Hypoxia-inducible factors (HIFs), which stimulate angiogenesis, can also be activated by ROS, and as a result, tumors can develop new blood vessels and stimulate their growth in low-oxygen conditions [9], [23].

In addition, ROS can affect the tumor microenvironment, causing inflammation and immune evasion, which are vital in cancer development [24], [25]. Nevertheless, as much as ROS are associated with the development and advancement of cancer, they also offer a therapeutic chance. The high levels of ROS that are associated with cancer progression are also what expose the cancer cells to other modes of therapy that cause an increase in the levels of oxidative stress. Targeted ROS-based cancer therapies are expected to exploit this weakness by enhancing ROS production in cancer cells, thereby causing cell death through oxidative injury to DNA, lipids, and proteins [26], [27]. This is a therapeutic approach premised on ROS-induced cytotoxicity, in which prooxidant drugs, radiation, and chemotherapy are administered to heighten oxidative stress and target cancer cells [28]. Although ROS-targeted therapies have potential therapeutic applications, several obstacles hinder their clinical use. Selectivity is one of the most significant barriers. ROS-based cancer therapies may also be resisted by cancer cells through increased expression of antioxidant defense mechanisms, including Nrf2 and glutathione, which counteract excess ROS and prevent oxidative cell damage [16], [29]. Besides, another problem is the heterogeneity of tumors in that various types of cancer cells have different amounts of ROS generation and antioxidants [20], [30]. This inconsistency makes it difficult to develop universal ROS-targeted therapies.

Moreover, due to chronic oxidative stress, cancer cells may activate adaptive responses that render them resistant to increased ROS production. For example, cancer cells can stimulate ROS-sensitive

signaling pathways, including NF- κ B and PI3K/AKT, which promote cell survival, proliferation, and apoptotic resistance [31]. Consequently, the defense mechanisms that cancer cells have developed to adapt to the high levels of ROS have become a significant obstacle to the success of the ROS-based therapy [32], [33]. Although several investigations and studies have been done on the use of ROS in cancer treatment, several research gaps remain to fully exploit ROS in treating cancer cells. Among the significant gaps, the knowledge of the exact molecular pathway by which ROS are involved in the tumor microenvironment and immune modulation is lacking [24], [34]. The ROS signaling pathways interact with other intracellular networks, such as DNA repair, cell survival, metastasis, and inflammation. Greater insight into how ROS regulates these pathways will aid in identifying specific therapeutic targets [35], [36]. Also, the wide variation in ROS levels across cancer types poses a challenge for developing a universal ROS-targeted treatment. Various cancers can have quite different ROS profiles depending upon their metabolism and antioxidant requirements [16], [37]. Thus, it is necessary to develop individualized ROS-based treatments, in which tumor vulnerability to ROS can be measured and addressed accordingly [25], [28].

To address the obstacles associated with ROS-targeted therapies, several mitigation measures have been proposed. The first method is the combination of ROS-inducing agents with the conventional therapies, including chemotherapy, radiation, and immunotherapy [27], [38]. The approach exploits the synergistic effects of ROS-induced cytotoxicity, increases the effectiveness of traditional interventions, and circumvents the effects of resistance strategies [39], [40]. For example, radiation therapy produces ROS that can be combined with ROS-modulating agents to enhance the therapeutic effect of radiation in cancer cells. The other approach is nanotechnology and drug-delivery systems to enhance the specificity of ROS-targeted therapies [41], [42]. It is possible to design nanoparticles and liposomal formulations that selectively target cancer cells with prooxidant drugs or ROS-modulators, thereby reducing the toxicity of normal tissues and enhancing therapeutic effect [26], [43]. In addition, biomarker-directed strategies that can identify tumors highly susceptible to ROS can be used to select the right patients and enhance cancer-specific therapies [27], [28]. This study discusses the molecular mechanisms underlying ROS generation and detoxification, their influence on cancer hallmarks, and emerging therapeutic strategies that modulate redox balance between ROS-mediated signaling and cytotoxicity provides novel insights for precision oncology.

2. Sources and regulation of ROS in Cancer

2.1 Mitochondrial ROS Production

The main source of intracellular ROS is the electron transport chain (ETC) in the mitochondria. Superoxide anion is produced in large quantities by the ETC. The five protein complexes (complexes I through V) that make up the ETC are in charge of producing ATP [44], [45]. Superoxide is produced during oxidative phosphorylation due to electron leakage from complexes I and III. The primary site of mtROS production is thought to be the NADPH-ubiquinone oxidoreductase complex (Complex I), which is made worse by outside variables like hypoxia [46],

[47]. When one of the electrons in NADH_2 that is transferred to the flavin mononucleotide (FMN) overflows and is transferred to O_2 , as well as when reduced flavin mononucleotide (FMNH_2) donates an electron to O_2 , complex I's hydrophilic domain may generate superoxide anion. Reducing equivalents created in complexes I and II are taken up by complex III (ubiquinol-cytochrome c oxidoreductase), which uses the Q-cycle operating mechanism to metabolize them [48]. Genetic and acquired abnormalities in the respiratory chain of the mitochondria may cause complex III to overproduce ROS. Therefore, it is yet unknown how complex III might contribute to the generation of gross mitochondrial ROS in steady-state physiological settings [49].

ROS generation is increased in cancer due to metabolic changes such as the Warburg effect and mitochondrial malfunction. Genomic instability is fueled by mutations in mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA), which further increase the production of ROS [50], [51]. Despite being encased in proteins that are just as protective as those found in nuclear chromatin, mtDNA is especially vulnerable to reactive oxygen species produced by the respiratory chain. In addition to the aging process and illnesses linked to advanced age, its mutations can cause several disorders. Research points to a connection between mitochondrial genetic malfunction and aging [52], [53].

Significant oxidative damage results from ROS's reaction with nitrogenous bases and deoxyribose sugar in DNA. Mutations, carcinogenesis, apoptosis, necrosis, and genetic disorders may result from this [54]. When nucleosomes that arrange DNA within chromosomes are disturbed, the compaction and coiling of DNA within chromatin are interrupted, leading to DNA fragmentation. Since chromatin is crucial for controlling gene transcription, changes to its functional characteristics may result in mistakes that cause mutagenesis [55], [56].

2.2 NADPH Oxidase (NOX) Enzymes

ROS are actively produced as a signaling mechanism by the NOX enzyme family. Breast, colorectal, and pancreatic carcinomas are among the tumors where overexpression of NOX1, NOX2, or NOX4 has been connected to oncogenic transformation and metastasis. These NOX family isoforms are all transmembrane proteins that carry electrons across cellular membranes to convert oxygen to hydrogen peroxide (NOX4) or superoxide anions (NOX1-3 and NOX5) [57], [58].

When NADPH first binds to the dehydrogenase domain, electrons are successively transported from the NADPH substrate to the FAD cofactor and finally to the transmembrane domain's two heme groups. Oxygen, which is reduced to produce superoxide or hydrogen peroxide, is the last electron acceptor on the opposite side of the membrane. NADPH oxidase, Toll-like receptor agonists, leptin, cytokines (IL-6, PDGF, TGF- β , and Tnf- α), and hormones like angiotensin II (Ang II) can all increase the production of ROS [59], [60].

2.3 Other Cellular Sources

ROS buildup is also influenced by peroxisomes, cytochrome P-450 enzymes, xanthine oxidase (XO), and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress responses. Furthermore, exposure to environmental carcinogens and oncogenic signaling (such as RAS and MYC) increase oxidative stress in the tumor microenvironment [9], [61]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that ROS, which are essential for controlling tumor genesis, development, and advancement, are more prevalent in cancer cells than in normal cells. It's interesting to note that ROS is said to have two roles in the formation and management of tumors [62], [63]. On the one hand, by controlling metabolism, proliferation, and angiogenesis, elevated ROS levels provide larger survival advantages. However, ROS are also an effective tool for inhibiting or eliminating cancer cells, which is important during radiation and chemotherapy. By controlling functional proteins such as GPXs, SLC7A11, and PARP-1, ROS-dependent apoptosis, ferroptosis, and autophagy-mediated cell death have been shown to inhibit tumor growth [20], [64], [65].

Xanthine oxidase (XO), which catalyzes the oxidative hydroxylation of hypoxanthine to xanthine and xanthine to uric acid, is responsible for the last two stages of purine metabolism in humans. Aging is linked to oxidative stress, immunosenescence, and inflammation, and XO is elevated throughout this time. Furthermore, endothelial dysfunction, a crucial process that causes a number of age-related illnesses, including cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), appears to be indicated by XO [66], [67], [68]. The ER oxidoreductin-1 (ERO1) protein is the main source of cellular ROS in eukaryotic cells, which are produced by the endoplasmic reticulum (ER). A healthy quantity of ROS is necessary for the formation of disulfide bonds, a crucial step in the machinery that folds proteins [69]. Furthermore, the ER releases of Ca^{2+} can cause the generation of ROS. The ER's Ryanodine Receptor (RyR), a Ca^{2+} channel, is regulated by redox-sensing thiol groups. Calcium can be released from the ER by activating the Ryanodine Receptor (RyR) by oxidation of its thiol sites [70]. NADPH oxidase hyperactivity and mitochondrial malfunction, two major biological sources of ROS, are intimately linked to dysregulated calcium transmission. Additionally, the ER expresses the NADPH oxidase isoform NOX4, which adds to the oxidative stress vicious loop within the ER [49], [71].

2.4 Antioxidant Defense Mechanisms

Enzymatic antioxidants like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), and peroxiredoxins, as well as non-enzymatic compounds like glutathione (GSH) and vitamins C and E, help cells prevent the buildup of ROS. To preserve redox equilibrium, cancer cells frequently upregulate antioxidant systems through transcription factors like Nrf2 [72], [73]. Toxic chemicals and excess ROS are examples of persistent or deadly stressors that upset cellular homeostasis, resulting in macromolecular damage, changes in cell cycle and growth signals, and ultimately carcinogenesis. Numerous studies have shown that the activation of the Nrf2 pathway decreases the sensitivity of cells to carcinogens, hence it deserves considerable study in the field

of cancer biology [74], [75]. While it is well known that Nrf2 activation can shield cells from a variety of stresses and toxins, uncontrolled NRF2 activation has been linked to a number of cancer forms. Cancer cell lines and tumor samples from lung, breast, esophageal, endometrial, and prostate malignancies showed constitutively high Nrf2 levels [76], [77], [78]. It is now generally acknowledged that aberrant activation of Nrf2 might further boost chemo- and radioresistance while also improving cancer cell proliferation and survival in oxidizing tumor settings. In fact, there was a negative correlation between Nrf2 levels in the tumor and the prognosis of cancer patients. Increased amounts of Nrf2-target antioxidant proteins, which combat oxidative stress, are responsible for the positive impact of Nrf2 overexpression on tumor growth and survival [79], [80], [81]. The main class of antioxidant enzymes that break down superoxide anions is constitutive SOD. Mammals have three different isoforms of SOD: extracellular Cu-Zn SOD (SOD3), mitochondrial Mn SOD (SOD2), and cytoplasmic Cu-Zn SOD (SOD1) [82], [83], [84].

Dismutase superoxide is quickly broken down by all types of SOD into the more stable ROS (H_2O_2), which is subsequently transformed into water and oxygen by either CAT or GPx. Although it can also be found in the cytosol or mitochondria, the highly effective enzyme catalase (CAT) is mostly expressed in peroxisomes. Aging and age-related illnesses are linked to its lack or dysfunction. Additionally, GPx uses GSH to catalyze the reduction of H_2O_2 to water [85], [86]. Age-related disorders are linked to the depletion or deficit of one of the four isoforms of GPx, which are GPx1, GPx2, GPx3, and GPx4. Additionally, by raising ROS, lipid peroxidation, and iron overload, GPx4 deficiency is linked to ferroptosis, a nonapoptotic kind of cell death [87], [88], [89].

All cell compartments contain large amounts of GSH, and the primary thiol-based defense mechanism against oxidative and electrophilic stress signals in the cell is the ratio of its oxidized/reduced form (GSH/GSSG). GSSG reduces H_2O_2 to H_2O and O_2 by giving it an electron. Furthermore, GSH is a cofactor for a number of enzymes, including GPx, which effectively inhibits oxidative damage and, in conjunction with glutaredoxin (Grx), modifies the redox state of proteins by reversible S-glutathionylation [90], [91]. Ascorbic acid, also known as vitamin C, is a hydrophilic molecule that exists in both reduced and oxidized forms. The effects of vitamin C are modifying as it is a powerful antioxidant that may reduce unstable biomolecules (nitrogen, oxygen, and sulfur radicals), prevent oxidative damage and lipid peroxidation caused by peroxide radicals, and regenerate vitamin E and other antioxidants in the body [92]. The major sources and regulatory mechanisms of ROS in cancer are illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Sources and Regulation of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) in Cancer

3. Oxidative Stress and Cancer Hallmarks

3.1 DNA Damage and Genomic Instability

ROS can cause oxidative DNA damage, including base modifications (e.g., 8-oxo-dG), strand breaks, and mutations that activate oncogenes or inactive tumor suppressors such as TP53. Chronic oxidative stress thus acts as a mutagenic driver of tumorigenesis [93], [94]. ROS are constantly generated during normal cellular metabolism, predominantly in mitochondria during oxidative phosphorylation, in peroxisomes, and via inflammatory processes. Under conditions of oxidative stress, the balance between ROS generation and antioxidant defense mechanisms is disrupted, resulting in excessive ROS accumulation [95], [96]. In cancer cells, elevated ROS levels cause direct oxidative damage to DNA by interacting with nucleobases and the sugar-phosphate backbone, leading to a variety of lesions, including oxidized bases, abasic sites, single-strand breaks (SSBs), and double-strand breaks (DSBs) [97]. This widespread damage interferes with normal DNA replication and repair, creating a substrate for mutations, chromosomal rearrangements, and structural aberrations, all of which constitute genomic instability, a hallmark of cancer progression. Persistent oxidative DNA damage has been shown to trigger mutagenic events that accelerate oncogenic transformation and tumor heterogeneity [98], [99].

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), although less reactive, can diffuse across membranes and generate hydroxyl radicals in the presence of transition metals, promoting base modifications, including the

formation of 8-oxo-guanine (8-oxoG), a highly mutagenic lesion. The presence of 8-oxoG can mispair with adenine during replication, resulting in G:C→T: A transversions, which accumulate over time in proto-oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes. When these lesions escape repair prior to replication, they become fixed as permanent mutations, facilitating clonal evolution in precancerous cells. The cumulative effect of such oxidative lesions can drive genomic instability that underpins cancer initiation and progression [49], [100]. Cells possess an intricate network of DNA repair mechanisms, including base excision repair (BER) for oxidized bases and single-strand breaks, and nucleotide excision repair (NER) for bulky lesions. However, excessive ROS can overwhelm these repair pathways or directly impair their function by oxidizing repair enzymes, cofactors, or DNA damage sensor proteins [101].

For instance, oxidation of glycosylases or apurinic/apyrimidinic endonucleases diminishes their ability to recognize and excise damaged bases. At the same time, alterations in checkpoint kinases impede cell cycle arrest, allowing cells to progress with unrepaired DNA. This combination of overwhelmed repair machinery and bypassed checkpoints leads to the persistence of DNA lesions, accumulation of mutations, and increased chromosomal instability, all of which promote tumorigenesis [25]. Beyond direct chemical damage, ROS can indirectly influence genomic integrity through epigenetic mechanisms. Oxidative stress can alter the activity of DNA methyltransferases and histone-modifying enzymes, leading to aberrant methylation patterns and changes in histone acetylation and methylation [102].

These alterations can silence tumor suppressor genes, activate oncogenes, and reorganize chromatin structure, creating regions that are more susceptible to DNA damage or replication errors. Such epigenetic and chromatin-remodeling effects of ROS provide a complementary pathway by which oxidative stress promotes genomic instability, reinforcing the mutagenic potential of ROS throughout tumor development [103]. In addition, Mitochondria represent a major source of ROS, particularly under conditions of metabolic dysregulation common in cancer cells. Dysfunction of the electron transport chain results in electron leakage and superoxide production, which can diffuse into the cytosol and nucleus. This mitochondrial ROS not only directly damages nuclear DNA but also perturbs signaling pathways that regulate cell cycle progression and DNA repair fidelity. This redox crosstalk between mitochondria and the nucleus links metabolic alterations to genomic instability [104], [105].

3.2 Cell Proliferation and Survival

ROS modulate redox-sensitive signaling pathways, including MAPK/EPK, PI3K/AKT, and NF- κ B, which promote cell growth and survival. Low to moderate ROS levels activate these cascades, whereas excessive ROS can trigger apoptosis or necroptosis. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) act as intracellular second messengers that modulate multiple signaling pathways governing cell proliferation and survival. At physiological levels, ROS reversibly oxidize cysteine residues on key regulatory proteins, including phosphatases and kinases, which alters their activity and

downstream signaling [106], [107], [108]. For example, ROS-mediated inactivation of MAPK phosphatases sustains activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), which in turn enhance transcription of cyclins, c-Myc, and other cell cycle regulators. This signaling supports G1/S phase transition and promotes the continued proliferation of tumor cells, even under oxidative stress. Persistent ROS signaling thus provides cancer cells with a growth advantage while subtly promoting genomic instability through replication under oxidative conditions [98], [109], [110]. Redox signaling intersects closely with metabolic reprogramming in cancer cells. ROS stabilize hypoxia-inducible factors (HIFs) under non-hypoxic conditions, driving expression of glycolytic enzymes and glucose transporters, which shifts energy metabolism toward glycolysis, which is a hallmark of rapidly proliferating tumor cells [111]. Concurrent activation of NRF2 further induces antioxidant and metabolic gene expression, maintaining ROS within a pro-survival range while supplying biosynthetic precursors for cell division. Together, these adaptations provide both energy and a redox buffer, allowing cancer cells to proliferate despite oxidative and metabolic stress [25], [112].

ROS also regulate the phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K)/AKT pathway, a central axis controlling cell survival, metabolism, and proliferation. Oxidative modification of PTEN, a tumor suppressor phosphatase, at its catalytic cysteine leads to reversible inactivation, resulting in the accumulation of phosphatidylinositol (3,4,5)-trisphosphate (PIP3) and sustained AKT activation. Activated AKT phosphorylates downstream targets such as mTOR, BAD, and GSK3 β , which inhibit apoptosis, promote protein synthesis, and enhance metabolic adaptation. This ROS-mediated PTEN inactivation is exploited by tumor cells to survive in high-ROS microenvironments and under nutrient or oxygen limitation, enabling continued proliferation [49], [113].

The balance between ROS-mediated pro-survival signaling and ROS-induced cytotoxicity determines cancer cell fate. Moderate ROS levels enhance proliferation and survival, while excessive ROS trigger apoptosis, ferroptosis, or regulated necrosis. Tumor cells adapt by upregulating antioxidant networks, including glutathione, thioredoxin, and GPX4 systems, to maintain ROS at a permissive level. This redox buffering capacity allows tumor cells to withstand oxidative insults from their microenvironment or therapy, supporting continued growth and conferring resistance to chemotherapeutic and radiotherapeutic interventions that rely on ROS-mediated cytotoxicity [103], [114], [115]. ROS also influence cell cycle progression by modulating cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs) and checkpoint proteins. Oxidative modifications can accelerate G1/S and G2/M transitions by transiently inhibiting checkpoint controls, bypassing growth-suppressive signals, and promoting uncontrolled cell division. In combination with aberrant signaling from MAPK and PI3K/AKT pathways, this redox-mediated dysregulation of the cell cycle contributes to the hallmark uncontrolled proliferation of cancer cells, facilitating tumor progression and expansion within oxidative microenvironments [116], [117].

3.3 Angiogenesis and Metastasis

ROS stabilize hypoxia-inducible factor 1-alpha (HIF-1 α), upregulating vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and promoting angiogenesis. Furthermore, oxidative stress enhances epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) and matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) activation, facilitating metastasis. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are key regulators of tumor angiogenesis, the formation of new blood vessels from pre-existing vasculature. ROS stabilize HIF-1 α , even under normoxic conditions, promoting transcription of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and angiopoietins. These pro-angiogenic factors stimulate endothelial cell proliferation, migration, and tube formation, supporting neovascularization within the tumor microenvironment. Enhanced vascular networks provide oxygen and nutrients to proliferating tumor cells and facilitate tumor growth, while ROS-mediated modulation of VEGF signaling also primes endothelial cells for sprouting and remodeling [118]. ROS directly influence endothelial dynamics by affecting cytoskeletal organization, cell-cell junctions, and interactions with the extracellular matrix. Moderate ROS levels enhance endothelial cell motility, promoting sprouting and extension of nascent vessel networks. However, excessive ROS disrupts adherens junctions and tight junction proteins, increasing vascular permeability. This results in abnormal, leaky tumor vessels, elevated interstitial fluid pressure, and irregular blood flow, which together facilitate tumor progression and create heterogeneous oxygenation conditions that promote selection of aggressive cancer phenotypes [87], [119].

Oxidative stress contributes to epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) in cancer cells, a critical step in metastasis. ROS regulate EMT transcription factors such as Snail, Twist, and ZEB1, and modulate the expression of cell adhesion molecules like E-cadherin and N-cadherin. This redox-mediated regulation drives the transition of epithelial tumor cells to a mesenchymal phenotype, increasing motility, invasiveness, and the ability to disseminate from the primary tumor site. By promoting EMT, ROS directly enhances the metastatic potential of tumor cells [120], [121]. During metastatic colonization, circulating tumor cells encounter oxidative stress in the bloodstream and in secondary tissue microenvironments. ROS modulate adhesion molecule expression, cytoskeletal remodeling, and survival signaling, enhancing the ability of tumor cells to adhere to new sites, evade anoikis, and establish secondary tumors. This redox-regulated survival and colonization highlight the role of ROS as integrative mediators of the metastatic cascade [25], [122].

3.4 Immune Evasion

ROS modulate immune signaling within the tumor microenvironment by altering cytokine production and impairing T-cell function. Tumor-derived ROS can suppress cytotoxic lymphocytes and promote the differentiation of myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSCs). Thereby fostering immune escape. Oxidative stress within the tumor microenvironment impairs adaptive immune responses by inhibiting T-cell receptor signaling and downstream activation

pathways. High ROS levels reduce cytokine production, impair cytotoxic function, and drive T-cell exhaustion. This creates an environment in which tumor cells can evade recognition and destruction by cytotoxic lymphocytes, facilitating immune escape and tumor persistence [118], [123]. Innate immune cells are similarly affected by redox imbalance. Natural killer (NK) cells show diminished cytolytic activity under oxidative stress, while macrophages polarize toward a pro-tumor M2 phenotype. ROS-mediated changes in macrophage polarization result in increased secretion of anti-inflammatory cytokines, angiogenic factors, and growth signals, collectively supporting tumor survival, suppressing effective immune responses, and creating a permissive microenvironment for tumor progression [25], [38].

ROS facilitates recruitment and activation of immunosuppressive cell populations, including MDSCs and regulatory T cells (Tregs). These cells secrete inhibitory cytokines, suppress effector T-cell function, and reinforce immunosuppressive networks, allowing tumors to escape both innate and adaptive immune surveillance. Redox-mediated expansion of these cell populations contributes to sustained immune evasion [87]. ROS impair dendritic cell maturation, antigen processing, and presentation, reducing expression of major histocompatibility complex molecules and co-stimulatory signals necessary for T-cell priming. This weakens adaptive immune activation and fosters tolerance to tumor-associated antigens. By blunting antigen presentation, oxidative stress diminishes the immune system's ability to recognize and eliminate malignant cells [116]. Oxidative stress also integrates with inflammatory signaling pathways, including NF- κ B and STAT-3, to enhance the expression of immunosuppressive cytokines and checkpoint molecules, such as PD-L1. These interactions amplify pro-tumor inflammation while suppressing antitumor immune activation, sustaining a microenvironment that favors immune evasion and disease progression [103], [124]. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) drive multiple cancer hallmarks by promoting proliferative signaling, genomic instability, angiogenesis, metastasis, and immune evasion. These interconnected roles are summarized in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of how reactive oxygen species (ROS) drive cancer progression by inducing DNA damage, promoting cell proliferation and survival, enhancing angiogenesis and metastasis, and facilitating immune evasion.

4. Therapeutic Targeting of Redox Balance in Cancer

Oncogene activation, metabolic reorganisation, and mitochondrial dysfunction cause cancer cells to exhibit elevated basal levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) compared with normal cells. This chronic oxidative stress helps tumours to develop, but it also leaves an intrinsic weakness: cancer cells are at or near their redox tolerance limit. They are therefore exceptionally sensitive to additional increases in ROS levels. This basic biological difference underpins the redox-based anticancer approach. Redox-based therapeutic interventions against cancer can also be broadly divided into two conflicting yet complementary approaches: (i) pro-oxidant approaches that increase redox levels in the cancer cell to the point of induction of redox-dependent apoptosis; (ii) antioxidant-targeting approaches that disrupt the redox defence mechanisms that cancer cells rely on to survive. Moreover, ROS modulation, in combination with conventional oncology treatments such as radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and immunotherapy, is a rapidly advancing field in precision oncology [125], [126], [127].

4.1 Prooxidant Therapies

Anti-oxidant therapeutic approaches that target the increased ROS susceptibility inherent to malignant cells increase intracellular oxidative stress levels, thereby exceeding cytotoxic thresholds. One of the reasons why this approach has been chosen is the relative insensitivity of

cancer cells compared to normal cells to an oxidative insult: due to the already existing elevated levels of basal ROS and reduced anti-oxidant reserve capacity, exogenous generation of ROS is more easily triggered to cause apoptosis, ferroptosis, or necroptosis in tumour cells but not in normal tissues [126], [128]. A variety of clinically approved chemotherapeutic agents achieve their cytotoxic effects by generating ROS. The semiquinone and quinone forms of Doxorubicin are a common anthracycline antibiotic applied in the breast, ovarian, and hematologic malignancies, in which redox cycling of the drug gives rise to the formation of superoxide anion radicals and then hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Nonetheless, doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity, explained by excessive ROS accumulation in cardiomyocytes with insufficient antioxidant protection, is an important clinical problem, which is why the development of tumour-selective delivery methods is necessary [129].

Arsenic trioxide (ATO, As_2O_3) which was approved against acute promyelocytic leukemia (APL) acts by dual redox process: on the one hand, it directly inhibits glutathione peroxidase and thioredoxin reductase (TrxR), therefore, preventing the removal of ROS, and on the other, it causes the mitochondrial production of ROS due to the interference with the electron transport chain. In APL, ATO is a tumour-killing biological agent that has been shown to achieve complete remission in monotherapy, providing clinical validity for the concept of ROS-mediated tumour killing [125], [128]. Elesclomol (STA-4783) is a small-molecule copper chelator that delivers copper ions to the mitochondrial matrix, where they induce hydroxyl radical generation by a Fenton-like reaction. Preclinical models have demonstrated broad antitumor activity, and a Phase III trial has indicated that it enhances progression-free survival in stage IV melanoma and significantly improves it in patients with normal serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), which is strongly associated with greater mitochondrial oxidative metabolism and greater sensitivity to ROS [128]. One of the attractive approaches to drug repurposing is that of disulfiram-copper (DSF-Cu) complexes. The anti-alcohol dependence drug disulfiram forms bis (dithiocarbamate) complexes with copper ions *in vivo*, thereby inhibiting the 26S proteasome, triggering the p97-NPL4 pathway, and producing intracellular ROS. Several retrospective studies and preliminary clinical trials have reported improved survival rates in cancer patients who used disulfiram throughout chemotherapy. DF-Cu with carboplatin/paclitaxel Phase I/II trial (NCT02671890) is currently ongoing in advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC) [130].

New photodynamic therapy (PDT) technologies are a spatially selective form of pro-oxidant modality. PDT includes the use of a tumour-targeting photosensitizer (e.g., Photofrin, 5-aminolevulinic acid, Temoporfin) and light activation, which delivers energy to molecular oxygen to produce singlet oxygen (1O_2)- a highly reactive non-radical ROS which causes lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial membrane rupture, and immunogenic tumour cell death. PDT has now been approved for the treatment of oesophageal, lung, and skin malignancies. Current studies are directed toward near-infrared-activable photosensitizers with improved tissue penetration to expand their use to solid tumours [106], [131].

4.2 Targeting Antioxidant Defence Systems

An entirely different and complementary mechanism is the conceptual degradation of the antioxidant defence system, whereby cancer cells rely heavily on it to survive under sustained, constitutive oxidative stress. Adaptively, cancer cells overexpress the glutathione (GSH) system, the thioredoxin (Trx) system, and the Nrf2-Keap1 transcriptional axis, thereby forming targetable redox vulnerabilities. Interference with such protective mechanisms disrupts redox homeostasis, leading to oxidative cell death with selective targeting of cancer cells [132], [133]. The most common intracellular antioxidant is glutathione (GSH), which is found in millimolar amounts in cancer cells and catalyses the neutralisation of ROS by glutathione peroxidase (GPx). The prototypic GSH depletion agent Buthionine sulfoximine (BSO) competitively inhibits the rate-limiting enzyme in GSH production, gamma-glutamylcysteine synthetase (gamma-GCS). Preclinical research further showed that BSO and melphalan exhibited striking synergy in childhood neuroblastoma, prompting a Phase I clinical study that revealed the potential of BSO-mediated GSH depletion in pediatric malignancies. More recently, erastin and other system Xc-inhibitors deprive cancer cells of cysteine, the rate-limiting amino acid for GSH synthesis, and inactivate GPX4, resulting in ferroptosis and lipid peroxidation, types of iron-dependent oxidative cell death with therapeutic potential across various tumour types [132], [133]. The main secondary antioxidant pathway is the thioredoxin (Trx) system, which includes thioredoxin (Trx1/2), thioredoxin reductase (TrxR1/2), and NADPH, and has critical functions in DNA synthesis, protein folding, and redox signalling. TrxR1 overexpression in a variety of tumours is associated with resistance to chemotherapy and a negative outcome. Auranofin (Ridaura) is an antirheumatic medication that is a potent, irreversible TrxR inhibitor, achieved by covalent selenocysteine formation at the enzyme's active site upon gold(I) addition. Auranofin induces apoptosis by increasing mitochondrial ROS and is in Phase I/II clinical trials for the treatment of chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL), lung, and ovarian cancers. The reduced catalase level in cancer cells makes them more dependent on TrxR than normal cells, thereby providing therapeutic selectivity [133], [134].

4.3 Combining ROS Modulation with Conventional Therapies

The combination of ROS modulation and the currently used cancer treatment methods, such as chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and immunotherapy, is one of the most rapidly developing fields in translational oncology. The combination rationalisation behind the use of combinatorics is based on mechanistic synergy: ROS-modulating agents can sensitise tumour cells to traditional cytotoxic therapy, circumvent resistance, and augment immune-mediated tumour elimination [135], [136]. The cytotoxic action of ionising radiation (IR) is due mainly to the formation of hydroxyl radicals through radiolysis of intracellular water that causes irreparable DNA breaks in the form of double-stranded breaks (DSBs) in the replicating tumour cells. Intratumoral hypoxia restricts radiation-generated ROS, leading to radioresistance. Hypoxic radiosensitizers (e.g. nimorazole, tirapazamine) and direct ROS amplifiers have been developed to address this drawback. Ato has

been shown to have radiosensitising effects in glioblastoma and hepatocellular carcinoma through GSH depletion and inhibition of DNA repair. Moreover, cancer stem cells (CSCs), which are proportionately the major culprits of radioresistance and tumour recurrence, exhibit lower ROS levels due to higher antioxidant expression; targeting this radioresistance pathway could be achieved by targeting CSC antioxidant systems [106], [135]. The most significant paradigm shift between redox biology and cancer treatment is perhaps the convergence of ROS modulation and cancer immunotherapy. One type of regulated cell death, called immunogenic cell death (ICD), occurs in response to specific pro-oxidant stimuli and is characterised by the surface exposure of calreticulin (ecto-CRT), ATP secretion, a find-me signal, and HMGB1 release, a danger signal. The combined effects of these damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) include stimulation of dendritic cells, cross-presentation of tumour antigens, and activation of cytotoxic T lymphocyte (CTL) responses. The main inducers of ICD, such as anthracyclines, oxaliplatin, cyclophosphamide, and PDT, share a common mechanism: they cause ER stress and ROS production in mitochondria [136], [137].

Oxidative modification of PD-L1 by ROS at cysteine residues may affect its stability, glycosylation, and interaction with PD-1, thereby altering the response to checkpoint inhibitors. The synergistic antitumor activity of pro-oxidant agents, when combined with anti-PD-1 antibodies, has transformed immunologically cold tumours into immunologically hot tumours, thereby enabling checkpoint blockade. Several Phase I/II clinical trials are ongoing to test this combination strategy in a variety of solid tumour histologies [134], [136]. Although antioxidant supplementation (vitamins C, E, N-acetylcysteine, selenium) has been commonly recommended to reduce chemotherapy-induced toxicity, accumulating preclinical and clinical evidence has suggested that pharmacological antioxidant supplementation during active cancer therapy may, rather than substantially reduce, therapeutic effectiveness. The existing guidelines on consensus have suggested no regular high-dose antioxidant supplementation during radiotherapy and platinum-based chemotherapy until conclusive results from prospective studies are available [106], [137].

Nanotechnology platforms can be used to address the selectivity challenges of systemic ROS modulation. Fenton and Fenton-like reactions catalysed by iron oxide nanoparticles and copper-based metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are deactivated in the acidic, H₂O₂-rich tumour microenvironment at interstitial levels, producing highly toxic hydroxyl radicals selectively at the tumour site: a strategy known as chemodynamic therapy (CDT). Nanoplatforms loaded with glucose oxidase (GOx) use intratumoral glucose to catalyse the production of H₂O₂ in the tumour, which in turn starves cancer cells by serving as a metabolic substrate. It produces hydroxyl radicals through the Fenton reaction. These methods constitute an excellent combination of tumour microenvironment hijacking and targeted ROS amplification, with several nanoformulations undergoing Phase I trials [134], [138]. A summary of redox-targeted therapeutic strategies in cancer is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Summary of Redox-Targeted Therapeutic Strategies in Cancer

Strategy	Key Agents	Mechanism of Action	Cancer Types	Clinical Status	Advantages	References
Pro-Oxidant Therapy	Doxorubicin, Arsenic trioxide (ATO), β -lapachone, Elesclomol	Redox cycling; superoxide via mitochondrial ETC disruption; exceeds cytotoxic ROS threshold.	Leukaemia, APL, solid tumours	Approved / Phase I-III	Selective cancer cell killing due to elevated basal ROS	[125], [128]
GSH Synthesis Inhibition	Buthionine sulfoximine (BSO), Erastin, Imuthiol	Inhibits γ -GCS; depletes GSH; erastin blocks system Xc- causing GPX4-mediated ferroptosis	Melanoma, ovarian, neuroblastoma, glioblastoma	Phase I-II	Sensitises drug-resistant tumours; induces ferroptosis	[132], [133]
Thioredoxin System Inhibition	Auranofin (TrxR inhibitor), PX-12, PMX464	Covalent TrxR selenocysteine modification; impairs peroxiredoxin recycling; elevates ROS	lung, ovarian, colorectal cancer	Phase I-II	Well-tolerated; repurposed gold-based drug	[133], [134]
Nrf2 Pathway Suppression	ML385, Brusatol, Trigonelline, Halofuginone	Blocks Nrf2-Keap1 axis; reduces NQO1, HO-1, GPx; sensitizes to oxidative damage	Lung, pancreatic, liver, breast cancer	Preclinical / Phase I	Overcomes chemoresistance; broad spectrum	[131], [132]
Radiotherapy and ROS Modulation	Ionising radiation \pm nimorazole, ATO	Hydroxyl radicals via water radiolysis; ROS amplifiers enhance DNA DSB formation.	Head & neck, brain, breast, prostate	Standard of care and trials	Well-established; synergistic with antioxidant inhibition	[106], [135]

Photodynamic Therapy (PDT)	Photofrin, Talaporfin, 5-ALA, Temoporfin	Photosensitizer + light → singlet oxygen (¹ O ₂); oxidizes lipids, proteins, nucleic acids	Skin, oesophageal, lung, bladder, H&N	Approved / Phase II–III	Tumour-localised; minimal systemic toxicity	[136], [137]
ROS + Immunotherapy Combination	Anti-PD-1/PD-L1 + pro-oxidant agents	Induces ICD; releases DAMPs (CRT, HMGB1, ATP); activates DCs; enhances checkpoint blockade	Melanoma, NSCLC, colorectal, bladder	Phase I–III	Converts 'cold' to 'hot' tumours; broadens IO response	[134], [136]
Nanoparticle-Based CDT	Iron oxide NPs, Cu-MOFs, GOx nanoplatfoms, TiO ₂ -NPs	Fenton/Fenton-like reactions; tumor microenvironment H ₂ O ₂ amplification; chemodynamic therapy	Liver, breast, glioma, lung cancer	Preclinical / Phase I	Spatially controlled ROS; reduced systemic toxicity	[134], [138]

5. Oxidative Stress and Cancer Metabolism

Metabolic reprogramming in cancer cells is tightly linked to ROS regulation. Elevated glycolysis and pentose phosphate pathway activity generate NADPH, a critical reducing equivalent for antioxidant defense. Cancer cells exist under persistently elevated oxidative stress due to heightened metabolic activity, mitochondrial abnormalities, and oncogene-driven signaling. Rather than eliminating ROS, malignant cells maintain ROS within a narrow range that supports proliferative signaling while preventing cytotoxic damage. This controlled redox state is achieved through metabolic adaptations that enhance antioxidant capacity, particularly increased diversion of glucose into pathways that produce reducing equivalents. Such regulation enables tumor cells to tolerate oxidative conditions that would otherwise compromise cellular integrity [98], [139], [140]. A central component of this adaptation is enhanced flux through the pentose phosphate pathway, which supplies NADPH required for regeneration of glutathione and other antioxidant systems. By prioritizing NADPH production, cancer cells sustain detoxification of ROS while preserving biosynthetic processes essential for growth. This metabolic configuration distinguishes malignant cells from normal tissues and reflects the continuous demand to counterbalance excess oxidant generation [87], [141]. Mitochondrial dysfunction further contributes to oxidative stress by increasing electron leakage during respiration, thereby elevating ROS production. In response,

tumor cells often reduce reliance on oxidative phosphorylation and shift toward glycolytic metabolism, limiting additional mitochondrial ROS formation while maintaining energy supply. These coordinated mitochondrial and cytosolic adjustments support both redox stability and anabolic metabolism required for rapid proliferation [25], [142].

Oncogenic signaling pathways also actively remodel redox metabolism. Mutations affecting key regulatory networks alter glucose and glutamine utilization to ensure sustained NADPH availability, even under conditions of hypoxia or nutrient limitation. This integration of metabolic control with oncogenic activity underscores oxidative stress tolerance as a fundamental feature of malignant transformation and tumor maintenance [103]. Chronic exposure to oxidative stress induces durable adaptive responses that extend beyond immediate antioxidant defenses. Sustained ROS levels drive transcriptional reprogramming and metabolic remodeling, enabling cancer cells to maintain proliferation despite prolonged stress. These long-term adaptations are particularly important within the tumor microenvironment, where oxygen and nutrient availability fluctuate considerably [116], [143]. Redox-dependent metabolic plasticity allows tumor cells to dynamically adjust pathway activity in response to environmental changes. By continuously modulating ROS production and detoxification, malignant cells preserve redox-mediated signaling without surpassing cytotoxic thresholds. This capacity for rapid adjustment supports survival under diverse stress conditions encountered during tumor progression [87], [144].

The increased reliance on NADPH-producing pathways creates distinct metabolic dependencies in cancer cells. Disruption of these processes destabilizes redox equilibrium, leading to excessive ROS accumulation and impaired viability. Normal cells, which generally possess more robust baseline buffering systems, are comparatively less sensitive to such perturbations, highlighting a potential therapeutic window [120]. Consequently, targeting redox-regulated metabolic pathways has emerged as a promising anticancer strategy. Interference with adaptive antioxidant mechanisms can selectively sensitize tumor cells to oxidative damage while sparing normal tissues. This perspective positions oxidative stress adaptation not only as a survival mechanism but also as a critical vulnerability in cancer biology [116], [145]. Redox-dependent metabolic adaptations enable cancer cells to maintain redox balance and support rapid growth under oxidative stress. These metabolic reprogramming mechanisms are illustrated in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Oncogenic signaling and mitochondrial alterations elevate reactive oxygen species (ROS), while cancer cells adapt by enhancing glycolysis, pentose phosphate pathway flux, and glutamine metabolism to generate NADPH and sustain antioxidant defenses. This redox-dependent plasticity maintains ROS at pro-survival levels but creates a vulnerability whereby disruption of NADPH/antioxidant pathways causes ROS accumulation and cell death [146].

6. Challenges and Future Perspectives

6.1 Defining the Therapeutic Redox Window

The main obstacle that ROS-based cancer treatments face is the need to establish a specific therapeutic redox window that activates programmed cell death in cancer cells while protecting normal tissue from permanent oxidative damage [127]. Elevated basal ROS levels in cancer cells result from their metabolic and signaling defects. In contrast, normal cells maintain their normal ROS levels because both cancer and normal cells need ROS to support vital biological functions, including signal transduction, immune system activation, and tissue repair [147]. The process of systemic ROS modulation poses a significant risk because any increase beyond the toxic threshold will cause complete damage to DNA, proteins, and lipids in healthy cells, resulting in significant side effects and a complete breakdown of cellular balance [20]. ROS function through a complex mechanism that requires specific dosage levels, as low to moderate doses activate pro-tumorigenic pathways that lead to cellular changes and cell survival. In contrast, high-dose levels exceed a cell's capacity to handle antioxidants, leading to cell death via apoptosis, ferroptosis, and other forms of controlled cell death [148]. The clinical progress of several prooxidant agents has been severely hindered by an exceptionally narrow therapeutic window, which requires high drug concentrations to achieve therapeutic effects but results in dangerous toxicity to patients [127].

6.2 Tumor Heterogeneity and Spatial Redox Complexity

Tumorigenesis is a multistep process in which oncogenic mutations arising in a single somatic cell confer clonal advantage as the initiating event; yet mutations alone are insufficient for full malignant transformation, as additional epigenetic alterations and extrinsic environmental pressures including aging, chronic inflammation, and genotoxic insults must converge to drive progression toward an irreversible, highly heterogeneous, and invasive lesion [149]. Tumor heterogeneity refers to the diversity of cancer cells within a tumor (intratumoral) or between patients (intertumoral), involving variations in genetics, gene expression, and metabolism. This complexity, driven by clonal evolution operating under Darwinian selective pressures from both cell-intrinsic factors and cell-extrinsic microenvironmental stimuli including hypoxia, altered pH, and nutrient gradients generates phenotypically distinct and drug-resistant subpopulations capable of immune evasion, therapeutic resistance, and sustained uncontrolled growth, making treatment, diagnosis, and disease monitoring exceptionally challenging [149], [150]. Central to this tumorigenic cascade is the dysregulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), highly reactive oxygen-derived intermediates whose balanced intracellular levels are essential for normal homeostasis; oxidative stress defined as an imbalance between ROS production and antioxidant defenses contributes to DNA damage, genomic instability, and aberrant activation of oncogenic signaling pathways, while simultaneously fostering a pro-tumorigenic microenvironment that sustains cancer cell proliferation, survival, and metastasis [151]. Redox complexity arises not merely from elevated ROS levels per se, but from the dynamic tension between oxidant production and the adaptive antioxidant machinery that cancer cells co-opt to survive; the NRF2–KEAP1 signaling axis serves as the master regulator of this response, wherein oxidative stress releases NRF2 from its repressor KEAP1, enabling nuclear translocation and transcriptional activation of over 250 cytoprotective genes governing glutathione (GSH) synthesis, thioredoxin activity, and NADPH regeneration thereby establishing an adaptive redox buffer that, while protective in normal tissue, becomes a pro-oncogenic mechanism when constitutively activated in tumor cells [29], [151].

Sustained NRF2 activation in cancer, frequently mediated by loss-of-function mutations in KEAP1, enhances GSH synthesis, upregulates detoxifying enzymes, and promotes drug efflux transporter expression, collectively producing a multidrug-resistant phenotype that confounds therapeutic strategies [151]. The resulting redox complexity is further amplified by the heterogeneity of ROS thresholds across distinct tumor subclones, the compartment-specific nature of ROS generation from NADPH oxidase (NOX) and mitochondrial electron transport chain sources and the redundancy of parallel antioxidant systems, including both the thioredoxin reductase (TXNRD1) and glutathione reductase (GSR) pathways regulated by NRF2, all of which collectively obscure the precise oxidative switch governing the transition between tumor-promoting and cytotoxic ROS signaling, underscoring the urgent need for real-time redox profiling, subtype-specific intervention strategies, and biomarker-guided combination therapies [151], [152].

6.3 Adaptive Redox Plasticity and Antioxidant Resistance

Malignant cells exhibit a profound redox adaptation that enables them to survive chronic oxidative stress by developing an enhanced endogenous antioxidant capacity. This metabolic flexibility renders cancer cells relatively insensitive to additional stress inducers, effectively blunting the therapeutic efficacy of conventional treatments such as chemotherapy and radiation [153]. A cornerstone of this adaptive mechanism is the persistent activation of the NRF2–KEAP1 signaling axis; while NRF2 is typically targeted for degradation by the KEAP1–CUL3 complex under resting conditions, oxidative stress stabilizes the protein, allowing it to translocate to the nucleus [147], [154]. Upregulated glutathione (GSH) biosynthesis and thioredoxin system activity have been directly correlated with cancer aggressiveness and resistance to platinum-based chemotherapy and radiation therapy, as these systems enable tumor cells to neutralize apoptotic signals and maintain redox homeostasis. This targeted disruption of redox adaptation is increasingly viewed as a means to overcome drug resistance in advanced tumors [127], [154], [155].

6.4 Lack of Robust and Dynamic Redox Biomarkers

Redox-based oncology translation encounters a significant challenge because it requires clinically verified biomarkers that can measure intracellular ROS levels and metabolic fluxes in real time [147]. Current research often relies on static surrogate markers, including measurement of antioxidant enzyme expression levels (e.g., SOD and catalase) and assessment of oxidative damage product accumulation (e.g., malondialdehyde and 8-oxo-G) [20]. While these are useful for indicating past oxidative stress, they fail to capture the rapid, dynamic redox states and interconversions of specific oxidant species that characterize living tumors [147], [156].

This technical limitation leads to several clinical challenges. For example, Poor Patient Stratification as it is difficult to identify which patients possess the specific "redox phenotypes" most likely to respond to prooxidant or antioxidant interventions [157]. Researchers face difficulties evaluating tumor redox alterations because they lack access to real-time redox-monitoring technology that would enable more precise measurements. The study shows that nonspecific ROS dyes mislead data interpretation, underscoring the need for better scientific methods, including deep-tissue imaging and mass spectrometry [147], [158].

7. Future Perspectives: Toward Precision Redox Oncology

Recent progress in redox-sensitive biosensors and genetically encoded fluorescent probes such as FRET-based sensors that monitor metabolic cofactors and caspase activity now enables real-time visualization of ROS dynamics at subcellular resolution [157]. These advanced imaging tools offer

unprecedented insights into the rapid fluctuations in tumor-specific redox states, overcoming the historical technical hurdle of relying on static, nonspecific surrogate markers [147]. The integration of single-cell multi-omics, spatial metabolomics, and redox proteomics will soon enable precise mapping of oxidative heterogeneity across diverse tumor ecosystems [159]. This comprehensive mapping is essential for rational therapeutic design, as it accounts for the divergent metabolic phenotypes and ROS dependencies found within a single lesion, particularly in specialized subpopulations like cancer stem cells [147]. Future therapies will rely on personalized redox-targeted approaches based on tumor genotype, metabolism, and microenvironment. Identifying tumor-specific redox phenotypes can guide effective redox-based treatment selection [157], [160]. Furthermore, the rational combination of ROS modulation with chemotherapy, radiotherapy, ferroptosis induction, and immunotherapy has the potential to maximize tumor-selective cytotoxicity while minimizing systemic toxicity [161]. For example, combining ROS-generating agents with immune checkpoint inhibitors or radiotherapy can synergistically overwhelm cancer cells' adaptive defenses, pushing them toward regulated cell death without harming surrounding healthy tissue [162], [163].

8. Conclusion

Reactive oxygen species contribute to cancer development and represent potential therapeutic targets. Persistent oxidative stress leads to genomic instability, tumor progression, and immune evasion. This elevated stress positions cancer cells near their maximal redox capacity, creating a therapeutic window in which pro-oxidant therapies and inhibition of antioxidant defenses may be effective. Nevertheless, tumor heterogeneity, dynamic redox adaptations, and challenges in defining a safe therapeutic window constrain clinical application. Advances in real-time ROS monitoring and biomarker-guided patient selection may facilitate personalized treatment strategies. Modulation of redox balance holds promise for improving therapeutic efficacy, advancing precision oncology, and minimizing damage to normal tissues.

Funding: There is no funding available for this study

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) have no conflict of interest to declare.

Ethical Approval: Not Applicable

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